

ANALYSIS OF DEASES IN ELDERLY AND SENILE PERSONS, AFFECTING ACTIVE WORK ACTIVITY

Bokijonov Farrukh Azizjon ogli

Fergana Medical Institute of Public Health

Uzbekistan. Fergana city.

Abstract: *Elderly people are a rapidly growing socio-demographic group, constituting a fifth of the country's population, and by 2025 the number of people over 60 years of age will exceed one billion, which will account for 16% of the total population of our planet. In this regard, the problem of maintaining the quality of life of older people arises. The health status and morbidity patterns of older people differ significantly from those in other age groups. In this regard, the problem of health of elderly and senile people becomes relevant both for the Republic of Uzbekistan and for many countries of the world. Among the factors that determine public health, lifestyle factors and the availability of medical and social care play an important role.*

Key words: *elderly people, elderly patients, old age, morbidity, Fergana region.*

Purpose of the study. Conduct an analysis of the health status and clarify the risk factors and morbidity of older age groups of the population.

Research materials. The study was conducted at the Department of Therapy and Surgery of FMIOPH. The object of the study is elderly patients of the regional and city clinical hospital of Fergana.

A comprehensive retrospective study of the dynamics of the morbidity level of the population in the Fergana region over the years of independence was carried out using statistical observation methods (copied from the reporting data of the Fergana Regional Statistical Office).

Research methods. The study involved 391 people aged 60 to 85 years. All patients were asked to answer questionnaire questions characterizing their health status and possible causes of decreased quality of life and ability to work.

Results. The study divided 2 groups: 1st group - persons who maintained their working activity (173 people) and 2nd group - non-working patients (218 people). The ratio of age groups was as follows: group 1: 60-74 years - 82.8%; 75-89 years old - 19.2%; Group 2: 60-74 years - 63.9%; 75-89 years old - 36.1%. Women prevailed in both groups: women 58.6% and 67.6%, men - 41.4% and 32.4%, respectively.

The leading reasons for the decline in quality of life and ability to work among respondents were existing diseases: diseases of the cardiovascular system (57.5%), pathology of the urinary system (56.3%), diseases of the musculoskeletal system (48.3%), diseases of the broncho-pulmonary system (47.6%), gastrointestinal tract (28.3%) and nervous system (7.8%). It was revealed that only 26.2% of patients are registered at the dispensary. Patients of the 1st group attended scheduled, preventive medical examinations more often than the 2nd group and amounted to 28.3% and 10.1%, respectively. The frequency of visits to the clinic or hospitalization due to deterioration of health in the group of working elderly patients was less than in non-working patients (65.5% and 87.9%, respectively). It was noted that to maintain their health and physical activity, 67.3% of patients in the first group engage in physical activity (physical therapy, daily walking for 30 minutes, health groups, etc.). In the second group this figure was only 15%.

Currently, in the Fergana region, the trend towards a significant increase in the proportion of elderly people is becoming more and more clear. Thus, the share of people over working age over the past twenty-five years (1990 – 2020) has increased from 18.7% to 26.2%. The aging of the region's population will continue: according to Ferganastat's forecast, it will reach 27.3% by 2025. This trend will be typical for both urban and rural populations. However, the rural population will age faster (1.2 times). The aging of the population significantly affects the level and characteristics of morbidity in the population. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to study the attitude of older people to the main components of a healthy lifestyle. To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set: - to study the attitude of older people to the components of a healthy lifestyle; - characterize the psychological status of older people. The sample representative population consisted of 211 people. Among them, 56.8% are men and 43.2% are women. Attitude to one's health, level of knowledge of sanitary and hygienic standards, principles of a healthy lifestyle largely depend on the level of education. An analysis of the educational level of older people who passed through inpatient institutions showed that 74.0% of respondents had secondary education and only 26.0% had higher education. When assessing their health status, 62.0% of respondents rated it as "low," 32.7% as "average," and 5.3% as "very low." In terms of the structure of diseases among respondents, the leading diseases were diseases of the circulatory system (61.0%), diseases of the digestive system (16.0%), diseases of the respiratory system (13.0%), pathology of the musculoskeletal system (7.0%) and diseases of the nervous system. systems (3.0%). The majority of respondents had concomitant pathology. 80.4% of elderly people undergo a comprehensive medical examination annually. In addition, during the year, 62.2% of

respondents additionally sought medical help at the clinic at least 2 times, and 37.8% more than 3 times. At the same time, elderly people are less likely to re-visit the clinic, preferring annual inpatient treatment (77.2%), 63.8% of respondents, due to their clinical status, used sanatorium-resort treatment. Thus, it can be argued that the city's treatment, preventive and health institutions qualitatively implement all forms of preventive work among elderly and senile people. 60.9% of respondents assessed the work of medical institutions positively, but 39.1% had some complaints about the drug supply, the form of service and the not always correct attitude of medical staff towards patients. An important component of your lifestyle is taking care of your health. Our study showed that 98.0% of respondents systematically monitor their blood pressure levels and have a negative attitude towards smoking and alcohol. At the same time, 75.0% of elderly men rarely drink alcohol, and in old age this value is higher and amounts to 95.5%. Women have practically eliminated alcohol from their diet. Almost all respondents participating in the study try to follow a diet that limits salt and sugar intake. An analysis of the active lifestyle of older people showed that 47.4% of respondents reasonably combine sleep, rest and physical activity. At the same time, physical activity in 36.1% of respondents is realized through active morning exercises, and in 53.9% - through walking and hiking. One of the problems of old age is loneliness, which is associated with the loss of social connections and the loss of loved ones. During the study, it was found that 39.0% of men and 74.0% of women are lonely people, which significantly affects the quality of life of an elderly person and leads to frequent emotional breakdowns, depression, and exacerbation of existing chronic diseases. This pattern is observed among older people living independently (27.0% of women and 60.0% of men) and living in a family (73.0% of men and 40.0% of women). At the same time, a feeling of loneliness was present in 39.0% of respondents living in a family, despite good relationships with children and grandchildren. The identified problems were the basis for studying the psychological status of elderly people, since the moral and psychological climate, as a criterion of lifestyle, plays an important role in the quality of life. In connection with the assessment of the severity of personal, situational anxiety and its components using an integrated anxiety test, it showed that the majority of respondents had a high level of anxiety, with a predominance of the asthenic component. Emotional discomfort, anxious perspective assessment, phobic component, social defense reaction does not reach a high level of anxiety. Many of the respondents (70.0%) see overcoming a depressive state in working around the house and at their dacha, 4.% - in participating in amateur art groups and visiting "Health" groups. Despite this, identified mental and emotional deviations require psychological

support from both relatives and specialist psychologists, which will significantly improve the quality of life of an elderly person.

Conclusions. 1. People of the older generation are quite oriented in their pathology, take good care of their health and do not neglect the basic aspects of their lifestyle. At the same time, it is noteworthy that in terms of the main characteristics of a healthy lifestyle, women are predominantly in the lead (active cooperation with medical institutions, more pedantically observing diet, sleep and rest regimes), but in terms of physical activity - men.

2. An assessment of the psychological status of older people did not reveal any deep violations. 46.0% of respondents expressed increased situational anxiety, and 66.0% - personal anxiety, accompanied by an asthenic component, the formation of a certain emotional background in the form of self-doubt, concern about the future.

3. Medical and recreational institutions of the healthcare system sufficiently implement all methods of preventive work among elderly and senile people, provide highly qualified medical care, but, nevertheless, all elderly people need medical and social assistance, moral and psychological support for loved ones and socio-psychological adaptation with the active participation of social protection institutions.

4. Further improvement of geriatric care in the Fergana region will create conditions under which old age will be perceived by all people and each person individually as a worthy and full-fledged stage of life.

Recommendations. Physical activity for older adults can come in a variety of forms: recreational or recreational exercise, physical activity, household chores, games, competitions, sports, or routine activities as part of daily activities, family, and community.

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